

Cyclohexenone Derivatives. Part III. Studies in Their Formation by the Robinson-Mannich Base Synthesis*

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The condensation of 4-diethylaminobutan-2-one methiodide with a few β -oxo-esters, viz., α -methyl- β -oxo-adipate, α -methyl- β -oxopimelate, and β -oxovalerate, and some related reactions have been studied. The structure of the product has been unequivocally proved in each case and the results have been discussed in terms of steric and electronic factors.

During our studies on formation of cyclohexenone derivatives by the Robinson-Mannich base reaction²⁻⁴, we reinvestigated the condensation of 4-dimethylaminobutan-2-one methiodide with methyl α -methyl- β -oxoadipate(I), originally carried out by Robinson and Seijo⁵, and contrary to the observation of these workers, we obtained an acid-ester in high yield. A preliminary discussion regarding the probable structures of the acid and the mechanism of their formation has already been published⁴. We now furnish a complete structural proof for this and a few analogous reaction products. An attempt has also been made to interpret the results from the consideration of steric and electronic effects.

Three structures (V, VII, and VIII) could be envisaged, as pointed out in the previous paper⁴, for the above condensation product, depending on the direction of the aldol ring-closure of the intermediate dioxo-ester (III). Of these, structure (VII) is the obvious choice both from the subsequently known examples of analogous ring-closures (see for example, Birch and Murray⁶, Downes *et al.*⁷, and Wendler *et al.*⁸) and also from our previous observation on similar reactions using Mannich bases of aryl methyl ketones. Structure (VII) has now been fully substantiated on the basis of the following evidence:

(i) The acid-ester itself does not form any dinitrophenylhydrazone, but on hydrolysis it affords an unsaturated acid (LX), m.p. 90°, which forms a red dinitrophenylhydrazone. This is consistent with structure (VII) but not with the alternative one (VI). The latter is expected to react with ketonic reagents quite readily.

* A preliminary account of this work has already appeared.¹

1. Guha and Nasipuri, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 84.

2. Nasipuri *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2734.

3. Nasipuri and Roy, *ibid.*, 1960, 1571.

4. Guha *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1960, 37, 267; Banerjee and Sivanandaiah, *ibid.*, 1961, 38, 652; *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1960, No 5, 20.

5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 582.

6. *Ibid.*, 1951, 1888.

7. *Austr. J. Sci.*, 1948, 10, 147.

8. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 3816.

(ii) The result of *C*-methyl estimation (1.62/mole) and the UV absorption spectrum (λ_{max} 242 m μ ; log ϵ , 4.15) of the above acid, m.p. 90°, are clearly in favour of structure (IX) for it and structure (VII) for the original acid-ester.

(V) R = Me.

(VI) R = H.

(VII) R = H; R' = CO₂Me.

(VIII) R = Me; R' = H.

(IX) R = R' = H.

(X)

(XI)

(XII)

(XIII)

(iii) The acid-ester has been converted by esterification and catalytic hydrogenation into the saturated ester (X) and the latter hydrolysed to yield a crystalline acid, m.p. 133-35°, which is found to be monobasic and is therefore to be represented by structure (XII). The acid-ester (VI), on the other hand, would on similar treatment give rise to a dicarboxylic acid (XIII).

(iv) Finally, the structure of the reduced acid (XII) has been confirmed by an unambiguous synthesis. For this purpose, ethyl 5-oxohexanoate⁹ was condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate according to the procedure of Banerjee and Shafer¹⁰ and the product on successive hydrogenation, alkylation with ethyl bromoacetate, hydrolysis, and esterification afforded ethyl 3-methylhexanoate-1,2,6-tricarboxylate (XI) in good yield. The latter was submitted to the Dieckmann cyclisation, the resultant β -oxo-ester alkylated *in situ* with methyl iodide, and finally hydrolysed to furnish 3,6-dimethyl-2-oxocyclohexylacetic acid (XII). This was found to be identical with the reduced acid, previously mentioned.

9. Dentley and Perkin (Jr.), *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1896, 69, 1510.

10. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1931.

The high yield (70-80%) of the acid-ester (VII) in the condensation of the Mannich base with α -substituted β -oxo-ester in the present case is presumably due to non-liberation of any water molecule from the aldol, the presence of which could have greatly reduced the rate of initial Michael addition (also see Logan *et al.*¹¹).

The reaction, seems however, to be quite useless for the original purpose of Robinson and Seijo, namely using the product for the synthesis of steroids, the substituted adipic ester in structure (V) functioning as a potential cyclopentanone ring.

Condensation of the Mannich-base with ethyl α -methyl- β -oxopimelate (II) followed an analogous pattern with one important difference that the product in this case was exclusively a neutral ester (XIV), the quaternary ethoxycarbonyl group being eliminated as a result of 1,4-*trans*-esterification of the intermediate aldol, followed by base-catalysed ring-opening.* This is in agreement with our previous observation that 1,4-bridged δ -lactone (XV) is formed preferentially to that involving the side chain. The ester (XIV) and its derivatives including 5,8-dimethylcoumarin (XVI), which was formed by dehydrogenation of the corresponding acid (as XIV), compared well with those previously described by Wendler *et al.*⁹ in another connection.

The reactions show that the aldol ring-closure of the β -oxo-esters of the type (III and IV) proceeds with the 'involvement of that carbonyl group which is flanked to the least extent by adjacent substituents' (cf. Henecka¹²). This generalisation is apparently supported also by the results obtained by Downes *et al.*⁷, Birch and Murray⁸, and Cardwell¹³ in similar reactions. The course of cyclisation thus seems to be guided entirely by steric factor and is contrary to that expected from the known greater reactivity of the terminal methyl group, and also from the slightly greater reactivity of the carbonyl group of a β -ketoic ester due to inductive effect of the alkoxy carbonyl group. The evidence for the latter argument can be found in the formation of Hagemann's ester (XX) by the action of 4-diethyl-

*Examples of such extensive decarbalkoxylation in appropriately substituted aldolate ions have already been cited in Ref. 4; see also Johnson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 2947.

11. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 4127.

12. Henecka, "Chemie der Beta-dicarbonyl Verbindungen", Springer Verlag, Berlin, 1950, p. 239.

13. Cardwell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 715.

aminobutan-2-one on ethyl acetoacetate, one of the earliest examples of cyclohexenone ring formation with the help of Mannich base¹⁴. The intermediate diketone (XVII) was later prepared by Cardwell and McQuillin¹⁵, who also confirmed its cyclisation to Hagemann's ester under basic condition.

From the above discussion it seems quite reasonable to expect that Mannich-base reactions with higher β -oxo-esters without any α -substituent, and thus without the extra steric factor due to it, may follow the course of Hagemann's ester formation. Accordingly, ethyl β -oxo-adipate and β -oxopimelate were allowed to react with the methoiodide of 4-diethylaminobutan-2-one, but very little product could be isolated in spite of best efforts. The same methoiodide, when condensed with ethyl β -oxovalerate¹⁶ (XIX) under identical condition, however, afforded 2,3-dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-one (XXI) in good yield, identified by its derivatives. Hennecke's rule is therefore still obeyed, the steric factor predominating over the electronic one. Exhaustive de-ethoxycarbonylation in this case is obviously due to 1,4-*trans*-esterification of the intermediate aldol.

It was next intended to study the effect of an α -substituent on the course of cyclisation of the dioxo-esters (as XVII; R=alkyl) with both the end groups being methyl. The methoiodide of the Mannich base of acetone was for this purpose condensed with ethyl α -methylacetoacetate. The product, predominantly a ketone, was identified as 3,6-dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-one (XXII), an authentic synthesis of which had already been reported¹⁷. The other possible ketone, namely, 3,4-dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-one (XXIII), was also prepared by lithium-liquid ammonia reduction of 3,4-dimethylanisole and was found to be completely different from the above product (see also ref. 17). This incidentally confirms one of the earlier experiments of Jacquier and Boyer¹⁸. One other example of such reaction is the well-known Walker's synthesis¹⁹ of piperitone by cyclisation of dioxo-ester (XVIII). We repeated the synthesis under our own experimental condition with the hope that extensive de-ethoxycarbonylation would occur as a result of *trans*-esterification, leading directly to piperitone. But we could isolate the cyclohexenone-carboxylate (XXIV) as the sole product. This is evidently due to large steric interference of the isopropyl group, inhibiting the formation of the bridged 1,4-lactone. A few examples of partial retention of alkoxy carbonyl group as a result of steric hindrance can be had in the work of Novello *et al.*²⁰. An attempt to condense ethyl α -isopropylacetoacetate with the Mannich base methoiodide of cyclohexanone with a view to elucidating this point, however, failed completely, the product consisting mostly of tar.

The results of the above experiments go to prove that the steric effect of the α -substituent predominates over the weak electronic effect exerted by the alkoxy carbonyl group of the β -oxo-ester system in directing the course of aldol ring-closure. A few analogous cases were also studied by Decombe²¹. The use of acid catalysts may, however, reverse the direction of cyclisation of the β -oxo-esters (XVII). Several such examples

14. Mannich and Fourneau, *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 2090.

15. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 708.

16. Anderson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2197.

17. Pyne *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 199.

18. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1955, 8.

19. Walker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1585; Hennecke, *Ber.*, 1949, 82, 112.

20. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 75, 1330.

21. Decombe, *Compt. rend.*, 1937, 205, 680.

are already known in the literature²². Experiments in this direction may be profitable and are in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

2,5-Dimethyl-5-methoxycarbonyl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylacetic acid (VII) was prepared according to the method previously described⁴. The maximum yield was found to be 70%, based on methyl α -methyl- β -oxoadipate and varied considerably, depending on the quality of ethanol used. The corresponding *methyl ester* was prepared by the action of an ethereal solution of diazomethane and had b.p. 155-60°/0.2mm. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 7.4. $C_{13}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 61.4; H, 7.1%).

2,5-Dimethyl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylacetic Acid (IX).—The acid-ester (VII) (4g.) was hydrolysed by heating with 10% ethanolic KOH (50 ml) for 5 hr. on a water bath. The gummy acid, thus obtained, solidified on scratching and crystallised from benzene-light petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) in thick white prisms, m.p. 90°. (Found: C, 65.7; H, 7.8; C-Me, 1.62; equiv., 182. $C_{10}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 65.9; H, 7.7%; equiv., 182). λ_{max}^{EtOH} 242 μ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.15). Robinson and Seijo⁵ record m.p. 80-83°. It readily formed a red DNP, m.p. 215°. (Found: N, 15.6. $C_{16}H_{18}O_6N_4$ requires N, 15.5%). The *semicarbazone* had m.p. 203-204°. (Found: N, 17.4. $C_{11}H_{18}O_5N_3$ requires N, 17.8%).

3,6-Dimethyl-2-oxocyclohexylacetic Acid (XII).—Methyl ester of the acid (VII) (2.5 g.) in methanol (20 ml) was shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen in presence of 10% palladium charcoal (200 mg.) for 6 hr. when one mole of hydrogen was absorbed. The mixture on filtration and distillation afforded the saturated ester (X) as a colorless oil (2.2 g.), b.p. 135-140°/2mm. It was hydrolysed by refluxing with 10% ethanolic KOH solution for 5 hr. on a water-bath, furnishing an acid, m.p. 130-31°. This was crystallised from benzene-petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) in white plates, m.p. 132-35°. (Found: C, 64.8; H, 8.9; equiv., 181. $C_{10}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 65.2; H, 8.7%; equiv., 184). It was found to be identical with a sample synthesised (*vide infra*).

Ethyl 3-Methylhexane-1,2,6-tricarboxylate (XI).—Ethyl 1-cyano-2-methylpent-1-en-1,5-dicarboxylate (10 g.), b.p. 160-65°/8 mm, prepared according to Banerjee and Shafer¹⁰, was hydrogenated in presence of 10% palladium-charcoal (500 mg.) in ethanol (35 ml), the absorption of hydrogen (1 mole) being completed within 2 hr. The reduced *cyano-ester* (9.5 g.), b.p. 160-65°/8 mm, was obtained as a colorless oil. (Found: N, 5.3. $C_{13}H_{21}O_4N$ requires N, 5.5%). It was used in alkylation reaction as follows.

A solution of the above cyano-ester (7 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (4.6 g.), and ethanolic sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (0.64 g.) and ethanol (11 ml), was heated under reflux for 10hr. in the water bath. The cooled product was decomposed with acidulated water, organic matter collected in ether, solvent removed, and the residue distilled to furnish an oil (7g.), b.p. 180-85°/5mm. This was hydrolysed by heating with a solution of KOH (10 g.) in ethylene glycol (25 ml) for 10 hr. Ethylene glycol was partly removed by distillation and the residue was diluted with water and acidified to yield *3-methylhexane-1,2,6-tricarboxylic acid* as a gum (3.5 g.), which was esterified with a refluxing mixture of ethanol

22. Blaise and Maire, *Compt. rend.*, 1907, 144, 572; *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1908, 3, 418.

(9 ml), dry benzene (16ml), and H_2SO_4 (conc., 1.5ml) for 24 hr. *Ethyl 3-methylhexane-1,2,6-tricarboxylate* (XI) was obtained as a colorless oil (2.2 g.), b.p. $150-55^\circ/3mm$. (Found: C, 60.3; H, 8.9. $C_{16}H_{28}O_6$ requires C, 60.8; H, 8.9%).

3,6-Dimethyl-2-oxocyclohexylacetic Acid (XII).—The preceding triethyl ester (XI) (2 g.), finely pulverised sodium (0.2 g.), dry benzene (20 ml), and a drop of methanol were refluxed in a water bath for 4 hr. The product was cooled in a freezing mixture, methyl iodide (2 ml) was added to it, and left overnight. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 5 hr. The product was worked up in the usual way and the crude β -oxo-ester was hydrolysed by heating with 2.5% aqueous KOH solution for 7 hr. The alkaline solution on acidification afforded *3,6-dimethyl-2-oxocyclohexylacetic acid* (XII) as a crystalline solid (1g.), m.p. $110-25^\circ$. This was purified by a few crystallisations from benzene-petroleum to yield the pure acid in white plates, m.p. $133-35^\circ$. (Found: C, 64.9; H, 8.8. $C_{10}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 65.2; H, 8.7%). The m.p. was not depressed when admixed with a former sample (*vide supra*). The keto-acid did not form any DNP or semicarbazone under the usual conditions.

Ethyl α -methyl- β -oxopimelate (II) was obtained by methylation of ethyl β -oxopimelate²³ (23 g.) with methyl iodide (7 ml) and an ethanolic solution of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (2.3 g.) and ethanol (40 ml) in the usual way. It formed a colorless oil (18.1g.), b.p. $139-40^\circ/2 mm$. (Found: C, 58.7; H, 8.5. $C_{15}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 59.0; H, 8.2%).

Condensation of 4-Diethylaminobutan-2-one with Ethyl α -Methyl- β -oxopimelate (II): *Formation of Ethyl β -2,5-Dimethyl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylpropionate* (XIV).—The methiodide of 4-diethylaminobutan-2-one²⁴ (7.5 g.) was condensed with the ester (II) (12.2 g.) in presence of potassium ethoxide, prepared from potassium (3.3 g.), ethanol (50 ml), and dry benzene (50 ml) as described in an analogous case⁴. The mixture was heated under reflux for 4 hr. and then worked up in the usual way. Only a very small amount of the acidic fraction (0.6 g.) was isolated by extraction with sodium bicarbonate solution; it was not investigated further. The neutral fraction on distillation afforded *ethyl β -2,5-dimethyl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylpropionate* (6.4 g.), b.p. $132-35^\circ/3mm$ as an oil. (Found: C, 69.2; H, 9.2. $C_{19}H_{26}O_5$ requires C, 69.7; H, 8.9%). It gave a red DNP, crystallising from ethanol in bright red needles, m.p. $105-106^\circ$. (Found: C, 56.7; H, 6.2; N, 14.0. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{24}O_6N_4$: C, 56.4; H, 5.9; N, 13.9%). The *semicarbazone* crystallised from methanol in white needles, m.p. 228° .

β -2,5-Dimethyl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylpropionic Acid.—The preceding ester (2.2 g.) was hydrolysed with 10% ethanolic KOH in the usual way to afford *β -2,5-dimethyl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylpropionic acid* (1.7g.) as a low-melting solid, m.p. 48° . (Found: C, 67.1; H, 8.6; C-Me, 1.71. $C_{11}H_{16}O_5$ requires, C, 67.3; H, 8.5; C-Me, 20%). λ_{max}^{EtOH} $242 m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.1). The *semicarbazone* crystallised from ethanol in colorless rectangular plates, m.p. $204-205^\circ$. (Found: N, 16.7. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{16}O_5N_3$: N, 16.6%). The m.p.s. of the acid and its derivative were in well accord with those recorded by Wendler *et al.*⁵

5,8-Dimethylcoumarin (XVI).—The above propionic acid (1.1g.) and 10% palladium-charcoal (800 mg.) were heated at 250° for 1 hr. The product was thoroughly extracted

23. Guha and Nasipuri, "Org. Syntheses", 1962, 42, 41.

24. Wilds and Shunk, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 469.

with ether and then sublimed in high *vacuo*. The sublimate after crystallisation from light petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) afforded 5,8-dimethylcoumarin (XVI), m.p. 120°. (Found: C, 75.8; H, 5.8. Calc. for C₁₁H₁₀O₂: C, 75.9; H, 5.7%). Wendler *et al.*⁶ report m.p. 120°.

Condensation of the Mannich Base Methiodide with Ethyl β-Oxovalerate: Formation of 2,3-Dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-one (XXI).—(a). The methiodide of 4-diethylaminobutan-2-one (8 g.) was condensed with ethyl β-oxovalerate (XIX) (10.8 g.) in dry benzene (40 ml) in presence of potassium ethoxide, prepared from potassium (3 g.) and ethanol (40 ml). After the addition of a further amount of potassium ethoxide (potassium, 1.5 g. and ethanol, 20 ml), the mixture was refluxed for 4 hr. Ethanol was partly removed in the water pump; the residue was decomposed with H₂SO₄ (cold, dil.) and extracted with ether. The product after distillation afforded a low-boiling oil (2.5 g.) b.p. 65°/10 mm; λ_{max}^{EtOH} 247 mμ (log ε, 4.07), n_D³⁶ 1.4465; it was identified as 2,3-dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-one (XXI) through the formation of semicarbazone, m.p. 226° (from ethanol) (Found: C, 59.6; H, 8.5. Calc. for C₉H₁₅ON₃: C, 59.7; H, 8.3%) and a dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 202° (Found: C, 55.2; H, 5.4. C₁₄H₁₆O₄N₄ requires C, 55.3; H, 5.3%). The mixed m.p.s. of these derivatives with those prepared from an authentic specimen of the ketone²⁵ remained undepressed.

The condensation product also afforded a higher boiling fraction (1 g.), b.p. 135-40°/10 mm, proved to be 2,3-dimethyl-6-ethoxycarbonylcyclohex-2-en-1-one by hydrolysis and formation of a dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 202°, from the resultant ketone. The relatively poor yield of the total ketone in this condensation was evidently due to loss of material during removal of the ethanol.

(b). 2,3-Dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-one was also obtained from the methiodide of the Mannich base and ethyl β-oxovalerate by a two-stage procedure²⁵. The methiodide (from the Mannich base, 7.2 g.) and ethyl β-oxovalerate (6.5 g.) were allowed to react in presence of ethanolic potassium ethoxide from potassium (1.85 g.) and ethanol (22 ml). 2,8-Dioxooctane-5-carboxylate (5.6 g.), b.p. 137-45°/3 mm, was isolated from the reaction mixture and treated with dry sodium ethoxide (from sodium, 0.7 g.) in dry benzene under reflux for 2 hr. 2,3-Dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-one (XXI) was obtained as the major product (2.5 g.) and was identified by derivatives.

Condensation of the Mannich Base with Ethyl 2-Methyl-3-oxobutyrate: Formation of 3,6-Dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-one (XXII).—Ethyl 2-methyl-3-oxobutyrate (12 g.) was condensed with the methiodide of 4-diethylaminobutan-2-one (10 g.) in presence of a solution of potassium (6 g.) in ethanol (80 ml) and benzene (50 ml), as described under method (a). The product on distillation afforded mostly a ketone (5.5 g.), b.p. 85-88°/13 mm as a sweet smelling liquid, n_D^{36.5} 1.4770; λ_{max} 234 mμ (log ε, 4.1). It furnished a semicarbazone in glistening flakes, m.p. 200-201° (ethanol) (Found: C, 59.5; H, 8.3; N, 23.2%) and a red dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 171-72° (Found: N, 18.8. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₅O₄N₄: N, 18.4%). The m.p.s. of both these derivatives remained undepressed when mixed with specimens prepared from authentic 3,6-dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-one¹⁷ (XXII) but were depressed considerably when mixed with those prepared from 3,4-dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-one¹⁷ (XXIII) (*vide infra*).

25. Smith and Rouault, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 631.

3,4-Dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-one (XXIII).—*m*-Cresyl methyl ether was chloromethylated by following a procedure of Quelet and Anglade²⁶ and the resultant 4-methoxy-2-methylbenzyl chloride, b.p. 110-15°/10 mm, was reduced catalytically, using 10% palladium-charcoal in acetone, to afford 3,4-dimethylanisole. A solution of this anisole (2 g.) in dry ether (10 ml) was reduced by lithium (1g.) in liquid ammonia according to Wilds and Nelson²⁷. The dihydroanisole, thus obtained, on acidic hydrolysis afforded 3,4-dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-one (XXIII) as a sweet smelling liquid (1g.), b.p. 80-85°/10 mm; $\lambda_{\max}$ 236 m μ (log ϵ , 4.2). The *semicarbazone* had m.p. 195-98°. (Found: C, 59.6; H, 8.4. Calc. for C₉H₁₅ON₃ requires C, 59.7; H, 8.3%). Pyne *et al*¹⁷. report m.p. 198-99°.

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26. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1936, 3, 2200.

27. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5360.